

FARMERS' AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE ON IMPROVED EARLY MATURITY COTTON VARIETIES INFLUENCES ADOPTION RATE BY SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN INDIA

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Abstract

Cotton as a cash crop has its prominent importance as it is used for textile purpose by large section world's population. It has a pivotal role in the Indian economy due to its direct and indirect employment and income generation in the agricultural and industrial sector. Cotton is grown as a major cash crop over larger area in Vidarbha region, Maharashtra state, of India. Still, maximum cotton cultivation area under rainfed conditions; acute moisture stress during flowering and boll formation; highly prone to insect pests and diseases due to green succulent leaves; long duration of crop are some of the major constraints in less productivity of cotton in the country. Improved cotton crop cultivation practices, integrated pest and nutrient management methods along with improved cotton varieties with early maturity and high yield has been developed by the research system. Though, the enormous development on the research front, still unawareness and non-adoption of the same is a restrictive factor in cotton productivity and ultimately in total production. Earliness is a desirable character which has several advantages. Early varieties permit multiple cropping systems, escape from late season pests, and reduce costs on pesticide sprays and crop management resulting in reduction in the cost of cultivation. The present investigation was carried out in Manasgaon and Masa villages of Buldhana and Akola district respectively of Maharashtra state. 80 cotton growers from these two villages were selected randomly to ascertain the extent of knowledge level and adoption level of the respondents towards early maturing varieties of cotton. The another aspect of the research endeavor to know the constraints expressed by the cotton cultivators in adoption of early maturing varieties of cotton as well as to access the suggestions expressed by them in adoption of the same. The study revealed that majority of the respondents had medium level of knowledge (52.50%) and (57.50%) adoption about early maturing varieties of cotton. The constraints like lack of knowledge about recommended early maturing cotton varieties; unawareness about benefits of growing such varieties; unavailability of seed; less technical knowledge regarding fibre quality etc. seems to be the major hurdle in adoption of early maturing cotton varieties/ hybrids as expressed by the farmers. The cotton growers suggested that, State agriculture agencies; KVK;s; State Agriculture University (SAU) should take initiatives through trainings, demonstration programmes, field days etc. for recommendation of the early maturing cotton varieties, and also make the easy seed availability to the farmers. So that the farmers could get adequate information about early maturing varieties; benefits of its adoption; technical knowledge about fibre quality and its measures etc. Respondents also suggested that, the SAU should proceed for development of new varieties/hybrids of cotton having early maturity; high yield with better fibre qualities.

Keywords- Cotton, textile purpose, cultivation practices, pesticide sprays

Introduction

Cotton is cultivated in 32.94 million ha area across eighty countries in the world. Traditionally known as 'white gold', cotton (*Gossypium Spp.*) is an important cash crop of India and its importance in Indian economy is reflected in terms of generating employment, and foreign exchange earnings. Cotton is the lifeline for about 60 million people who include farmers and workers involved in the cotton industry from processing to trading (*The Hindu*, 2007). Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh are leading states in terms of area under cotton cultivation across India. Cotton cultivation in India is 33.23 % of the total area under cotton in the world but has second position in production after China (Status paper of Indian cotton, 2017) with the estimated production of 36.10 million bales (1 bale=170kg) of cotton from 12.23 million ha during 2018-19 (CAB, 2018).

In India, cotton is cultivated in varied types of soils, climatic conditions and agricultural practices under rainfed (65 %) and irrigated (35 %) conditions. The maximum area under the cotton production in Vidarbha Zone of Maharashtra state, India is rainfed with only 23 per cent under irrigated area. The Vidarbha region has predominantly deep black cotton soil, suitable for *hirsutum*, *arboresum* and *herbaceum* cotton species. Hybrid varieties are grown as monocrops or as intercrops. The soil and climatic conditions under the study area is suitable for different early maturing varieties, released by agricultural university and Central Institute of Cotton Research, Nagpur.

Some of the major constraints of cotton cultivation area under rainfed conditions are acute moisture stress during flowering and boll formation; infestations by insect pests and diseases due to green succulent leaves and long duration of crop maturity, resulting in less productivity of cotton in the country. Improved crop cultivation practices, integrated pest and nutrient management methods and

improved cotton varieties with early maturity and high yield are preferred by the farmers. Although, there are number of improved varieties available, there is still lack of awareness and non-adoption of the improved varieties, leading to low cotton productivity and low production. To achieve higher level of productivity and maximize the returns from cotton cultivation, there is a need for creating awareness on improved varieties to encourage adoption by the farming community.

In rainfed conditions, earliness in cotton is one of the desirable traits with several benefits. Early varieties permit multiple cropping systems, escape from late season pests, and reduce costs on pesticide sprays resulting in reduction in the cost of cultivation. Since recent past years pink boll work is causing a serious damage to the cotton crops. In Buldhana districts of the Vidarbha region from Maharashtra state, India, 1.75 lakh hectares cotton crop was damaged by various pests including the pink bollworm, (*The Hindu- Agribusiness*, 2018). In cotton, maturity duration has been significantly reduced and most of the earlier cotton varieties mature in 240-270 days. Similarly, hybrids mature in 230-240 days. The maturity duration is reduced from 270 days to 170 days in case of varieties and from 240 days to 180 days in case of hybrids. Variety LRK 516 matures in 170 days and hybrid H 8 matures in 180 days. Early varieties/ hybrids have less incidence of pink bollworm compared to long duration varieties (*CICR, Tech. Bull.*, 2009).

Introduction of new farm technologies, plant protection measures and improved varieties created a large potential for increasing cotton production. But, cotton production largely depends upon the extent to which farmers adopt new agricultural innovations. Increased knowledge of farmers improves the adoption rate. In view of this, it is necessary to investigate the knowledge and adoption rate by farmers on early maturing varieties of cotton. Hence, the objective of the study is to study the constraints in adoption of early maturing

varieties of cotton in order to improve the adoption rate by addressing the cultivar needs of the farmers

Material and Methods-

The present study was conducted by using descriptive type of research design applying ex-post facto approach in Akola and Buldhana districts of the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state, India. These districts had predominant area of the region under cotton cultivation.

After brief consultation with Officials of the Agricultural Department and the University Scientists, two districts under the study, Akola and Shegaon tahsil were selected as maximum potential area under early maturing varieties. Two villages, one each from two tehsils, were selected randomly. After group discussion with cotton farmers, 40 respondents were selected randomly from each village. Thus, a total 80 farmers constituted the sample for the study.

Rogers and Shoemaker (1971) defined adoption as a decision to continue full use of an innovation. In this study, a teacher made adoption test was developed to measure the knowledge and adoption of early maturing varieties of cotton. For ascertaining the adoption level of respondents, were categorized into low, medium and high level of adoption on the basis of equal interval method.

The data were collected by means of individual interviews with questionnaires, which were developed for data collection and

appropriate statistical tools like frequency, percentage and ranking techniques, were used for analysis of data.

Results and Discussion

1. Knowledge level of cotton growers about early maturing varieties

Knowledge is the cognitive behavior of an individual. The body of knowledge is the product of learning process. Once the knowledge is acquired it produces changes in the thinking process of an individual which leads to further change in attitude and helps the farmer in making rational decision. Knowledge is prerequisite. On the basis of knowledge about the early maturing varieties of cotton the cotton growers classified into three types.

The findings contained in table 1 revealed that about 52.50 per cent of the respondents had medium level of knowledge. Around one fourth (26.25%) of the respondent were possessing high knowledge level, whereas 21.25 per cent of respondents had low level of knowledge.

It can be concluded here at marginally above three fourth (78.75%) of the respondents possessed medium to high level of knowledge about early maturing varieties of cotton crop. Still one fifth (21.25%) were recorded with low level of knowledge about the same. These findings are in conformity with the findings of Maraddi and Verma (2003).

Table 1: Distribution of respondents on the basis of their knowledge level about early maturing varieties of cotton.

S.N.	Category	Frequency	Per cent
1	Low	17	21.25
2	Medium	42	52.50
3	High	21	26.25
Total		80	100.00

Adoption level of cotton growers about early maturing varieties

The adoption of any technology is largely depends upon awareness and knowledge about the particular technology. Adoption is not

possible without the awareness and knowledge. Increased awareness leads towards the adoption process.

On the basis of adoption index the respondents were classified into three levels and data of the same are presented in Table 2

Table 2: Distribution of respondents on the basis of their adoption level about early maturing varieties of cotton.

S.N.	Category	Frequency	Per cent
1	Low	15	18.75
2	Medium	46	57.50
3	High	19	23.75
Total		80	100.00

It was observed that majority of the cotton growers (57.50%) belongs to medium adoption level whereas slightly below one fourth (23.75%) of the respondents were showed high level of adoption towards early maturing varieties of cotton while 18.75 per cent of the respondents were observed with the low level of adoption towards early maturing varieties of cotton. Thus, it could be inferred that, majority of the cotton growers had medium level of early maturing varieties. Our findings were supported by the findings of Landge (2001) and Bodake (2003).

Constraints –

From the study, some basic and major constraints perceived by the respondents were summarized in Table 3. The constraints like lack of knowledge about, early maturing cotton varieties recommended for Vidarbha region; non awareness about benefits of growing such varieties; availability of seed; technical knowledge regarding fibre quality etc. seems to be the major hurdles in adoption of early maturing cotton varieties/ hybrids.

Table 3: Constraints perceived by the cotton growers in adoption of early maturing cotton varieties/ hybrids

SN	Constraint	Freq n = 80	%
1	Lack of knowledge about early maturing cotton varieties recommended for Vidarbha region	20	25
2	Lack of knowledge regarding maturity of the varieties	68	45
3	Lack of knowledge about benefits of early maturing cotton varieties	64	80
4	Lack of technical knowledge regarding fibre quality and its measures	32	40
5	Non availability of cotton varieties having early maturity; high yield with better fibre qualities	24	30
6	Non awareness during selection of varieties for cultivation	40	50
7	More dependency on natural conditions for crop cultivation	64	80

Conclusion

The cotton growers suggested that, State agriculture agencies (KVK) and State Agriculture University (SAU) should take initiatives through trainings, demonstration programmes, field days etc. for

recommendation of the early maturing cotton varieties, and also make the easy seed availability to the farmers. So that the farmers could get adequate information regarding the recommended early maturing

varieties; benefits of its adoption; technical knowledge about fibre quality and its measures etc..

Respondents also suggested that, the SAU should proceed for development of new varieties/hybrids of cotton having early maturity; high yield with better fibre qualities. This will help to increase the knowledge of cotton growers about early maturing varieties/ hybrids of cotton and subsequently its better adoption too. Thus, the finding of the study led to the conclusion that the knowledge level and adoption status of cotton growers about the early maturing varieties of cotton was observed in the medium category.

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